

A Study to Assess the Efficiency of Planned Education Programme on Awareness about Extraction and Preservation of Breast Milk among Antenatal Women Visiting to OBG Department of Hanagal Shree Kumareswar Hospital & Research Centre Bagalkote

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Abstract:-

➤ *Background and Objectives of the Study:*

Nutrition is the basic needs of all human beings; even when they are in mother's womb as fetus. The fetus takes all nutritional necessity from his or her mother's womb and after birth baby will get its requirement from her or his mother's breast milk. Breast milk contains important nutrients for the whole growth and development of body and intellect; other than food, this is multi-use medication wealthy in anti infective factors which secure the infant. It improves the resistant system of the baby; as a result it will help in dropping the infant death rate. Objectives are to evaluate the obtainable stage of information concerning extraction and store of breast milk amongst antenatal women presence. To find out the value of planned training programme on information about extraction and storing of breast milk among antenatal women visiting to Hanagal shree Kumareswar Hospital & Research Centre Bagalkote to observe the association among post assessment information score of antenatal women about extraction and preserving of breast milk with their chosen characteristics of samples.

➤ *Methods:*

The present investigation is a pre experimental; the research was carryout between 50 antenatal women, using convenient sampling technique. One group pre-test post-test without control group design was used. The data was collected by using a structured closed ended knowledge Questionnaire. Data was analysed by using descriptive and inferential statistical in terms of mean, frequency

distribution, percentage, Paired t' test and chi-square test.

➤ *Results:*

In pre-test shows that the below mentioned outcome. Before the training in fifty antenatal women, maximum i.e. fifty-eight (58%) percentage of antenatal women have deprived information, (36%) of antenatal women had common information, (6%) of antenatal women have high-quality awareness. After the planned training, uppermost proportion (58%) of antenatal women had outstanding familiarity followed by lowly proportion (42%) of antenatal women with high-quality understanding about taking out and storing the breast milk.

The whole conclusion disclose that after the training the information mean score 24.84 which was 82.8 % of total score was more when compared to the pre-test knowledge mean score 12.98, which was 43.26 % of total score. As the premeditated t significance (19.97) was much upper than table 't' significance (1.96 one point ninety-six) for the Hypothesis. H₁: here is a considerable dissimilarity among before and after-training awareness values of antenatal women about extraction and preservation of breast milk.

➤ *Conclusion:*

The research provides that planned training programme about facts about extraction and preserving the breast milk of antenatal women was scientific, logical and cost effective strategy.

Keyword:- Antenatal Mothers, EBM, Efficiency, Planned Training Programme, Information, Socio- Demographic Characteristics.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nutrition is one of the basic needs of all human beings; even when they are in mother's womb as fetus. The fetus gets all dietary necessities by his or her mother's womb and after birth from breast milk. Breast milk contains impartial nutrients for the whole growth and development of body and intellect; other than food, this is multi-use medication wealthy in anti infective factors which secure the infant. It improves the resistant system of the baby; as a result it will help in dropping the infant death rate.¹ Breast milk is accepted as exclusive, accepted and nourishing foodstuff provided via the environment for infant². Recommendation by the American academy of paediatrics says in (2006) that human milk as the ideal foodstuff for all infants, as well as a sick newborn and to preterm babies' also³. Breast feeding is essential to wellbeing and development of kids and also essential to the mothers, it helps them to save from harm i.e. from breast cancer. As world says there is no alternate for mother's love, there is no better replacement for mother's milk. Also Breast milk is not only the greatest, but a necessity for the kids.⁴ Breast milk is safe and more secured diet for babies and protects them against sickness. It contains each proteins, fat, sugars, vitamins, minerals and in addition the anti infective factors.⁵ A little years ago; formula feeding was confident as a substitute for breastfeeding. Formula feeding was given by doctors as an option, merely when the mother is medically unhealthy to breastfeed. But community started captivating it for approved and used formula feeding in the position of breastfeeding but encountered with bunch of difficulty to their children. Now a day's most mothers are likely go to work and also during travelling they are unable to breastfeed their babies to overcome these entire problem, the mother can go for an alternative method for breastfeeding that is extraction and preservation of breast milk. Extraction refers that manually removing and safeguards the breast milk.⁶

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

An evaluative design used to judge the efficiency of planned education Programme on understanding on the subject of extraction and safeguard the breast milk amongst antenatal women.

➤ Study Design-

An evaluative approach was used to evaluate the usefulness of designed education Programme on understanding about taking out and storing of breast milk among antenatal women presence in OBG OPD of Hanagal Shree Kumareshewar Hospital and research centre, Bagalkote. The data was collected using a structured closed-ended questionnaire, and descriptive and inferential statistics were used to arrange and evaluate the results.

➤ Setting of the Study-

Research carried out in the ward and department of Obstetrics and gynecology Out Patient section at Hanagal Shree Kumareshwar Hospital and research centre, Bagalkote, Karnataka, India. An evaluative investigate approach was commonly useful where the prime goal is to find out the degree to which a particular approach meet the preferred effect.

➤ Participants-

In the present study, the sample consisted of 50 antenatal mothers and 50 mothers. They were selected using a non-probability convenient sampling technique.

➤ Instruments-

The study was conducted using a structured close-ended questionnaire. Information was gathered through an interview schedule using a structured knowledge questionnaire. It comprises 30 elements to assess about squeezing out and storing of breast milk among antenatal women, they were multiple-choice, and close-ended questionnaires. Each item was given a score of 0, and 1.

➤ Description of Data Collection Instruments

- **Part 1: Socio-demographic variables-** Comprised of 10 items to assess the socio-demographic variables of antenatal mothers.
- **Part 2: Structured questionnaire to assess information on the subject of extraction and storing of breast milk amongst women who were in antenatal period,** there were 9 items to assess knowledge about importance, 13 items on assess knowledge extraction. 8 items on assess knowledge preservation of breast milk

• Data Collection Procedures-

The main study was conducted between 21 November to 28 November 2019, in OBG Unit at Hanagal Shree Kumareshewar Hospital and research centre, Bagalkote, Karnataka, India. Data were collected from antenatal mothers through an interview schedule. Before the enrolment of subjects and data collection, formal authorization was obtained from the principal of the nursing institution, and the study's aim was explained to the participants. They were asked questions in Kannada and other languages understandable to them.

• Variable Under Study-

Study variable- the study variable for the present study were, Planned training programme, information on the topic of extraction and technique to preserve the breast milk, among antenatal women.

• Socio-Demographic Characteristics –

Age, religion, place of residences, type of family, family monthly income, educational status, occupational status, number of pregnancies, source of information,

➤ *Statistical Analysis:*

The obtained data were statistically examined in terms of the study's objectives using inductive statistics. A master sheet was prepared with responses given by the study participants. Frequencies and percentages were used for the analysis of demographic data. The mean and standard deviation were used as inferential statistics. The Chi-Square test was used to determine the association between insomnia scores and selected Socio-demographic variables of antenatal mothers.

• *Ethical Approval-*

A certificate of ethical permission was obtained from the institution's ethical committee, and written consent was taken from each participant.

III. RESULTS

➤ *Socio-Demographic Variables-*

In this research, the majority of antenatal women (50%) were in the age group of 20- 25 years, (60%)were Hindu,

(70%) were belongs to urban, (72%) were nuclear family, (40%)were having monthly income of 10001-15000rs, (36%) were studied up to secondary education, (50%)were house wife, (68%)were mixed diet pattern, (34%)were primi mothers, and(44%)were got information from health professional

Table 1: shows an assessment knowledge wise comparison of antenatal women in pre-test disclose the below outcome. Before the training programme among 50 antenatal mothers, the utmost proportion i.e (58%) of antenatal women had deprived information, (36%) of antenatal women had usual awareness, (6%) of antenatal women had good quality familiarity on the topic of withdrawal and safeguarding of breast milk. Conversely after designed education Programme (PTP) (post-test) highest percentage (58%) of antenatal women have outstanding familiarity followed by deprived proportion (42%) of antenatal women with high-quality facts as regards pressing out and preserving the breast milk.

Table 1 Percentage wise Distribution of Antenatal Mother According to Levels of Knowledge in Pre-Test and Post-Test N=50

Level of Knowledge	Pre-test		Post-test	
	No of respondents	Percentage	No of respondents	Percentage
Excellent	0	0	29	58
Good	3	6	21	42
Average	18	36	0	0
Poor	29	58	0	0
Very Poor	0	0	0	0
Total	50	100	50	100

Table 2 reflects that similarity of area wise mean and Standard Deviation related to awareness values in the area of "Importance of breast milk" after-test mean of awareness values in this part was 7.96 with SD ±1.01 which was 88.44% of whole values whereas before-test mean awareness values were 4.04 with SD ±1.13 which was 44.88% of whole values. The efficiency of planned education programme in this spot was mean awareness values of 3.92 with SD ± 1.32 which was 43.55 % of total score. In the area of awareness on Extraction of breast milk illustrate that after-examination mean understanding achieve was 10.16 with SD ±2.15 which was 78.15% of total score whereas pre-test mean information gain was 5.44 with SD ±1.90 which was 41.84% of total score. The efficiency of PTP in this region was mean knowledge score of 4.72 with SD ± 2.28 with which was 36.30 % of total score. In the area of knowledge

on "Preservation of breast milk" shows that post-test mean knowledge score was 6.72 with SD ±1.007 which was 84% of total score whereas pre-test mean knowledge score was 3.5 with SD ±1.004 which was 43.75% of total score. The usefulness of PTP in this area was mean awareness score of 3.22 with SD ±1.28 with which was 40.25 % of total score. The overall findings reveal that the post-test knowledge score 24.84 with SD ±2.87 which was 82.8 % of total score was more when compared to the pre-test knowledge score 12.98 with SD±3.06, which was 43.26 % of total score. The effectiveness of PTP on extraction and preservation of breast milk, mean awareness values of 11.86 With SD ± 2.90 which was 39.53 % of whole values. Hence it indicate the PTP was valuable in attractive the acquaintance of antenatal women.

Table 2 Area wise mean, SD and mean Percentage of the Knowledge Scores in Pretest and Post Test N=50

Knowledge area	Max. Score	Pre-test(O ₁)		Post-test(O ₂)		Effectiveness(O ₂ -O ₁)	
		Mean ±SD	Mean %	Mean ±SD	Mean %	Mean ±SD	Mean %
Importance of breast milk	9	4.04±1.31	44.88	7.96±1.01	88.44	3.92±1.32	43.55
Extraction of breast milk	13	5.44±1.90	41.84	10.16±2.15	78.15	4.72±2.28	36.30
Preservation of breast milk	8	3.5±1.004	43.75	6.72±1.007	84	3.22±1.28	40.25
Total	30	12.98±3.06	43.26	24.84±2.87	82.8	11.86±2.90	39.53

Table 3 reflect that the intended t value (19.97) was a lot superior than table 't' value (1.96 one point ninety-six) designed for the Hypothesis: **H₁**: Here is a considerable differentiation among before education training and after

education awareness values of antenatal women concerning extraction and preservation of breast milk. Hence the Planned Education Programme proved to be valuable.

Table 3 Significant Difference between the before-Test Knowledge and after- Test Awareness Scores of Antenatal Women N=50

Test	Mean	Mean Diff	SD Diff	Paired t- value	Table Value
Pre-test (O ₁)	12.98	11.86	0.19	19.97	1.96
Posttest(O ₂)	24.84				

Table 4 reflect that Chi-square was intended to discover the association among post test familiarity scores of antenatal women through their preferred social characteristics by the help of possibility table. Considered Chi-square report is slighter than table worth for socio demographic characteristics age ($c^2=1.281$, $P= 0.05$), religion ($c^2= 0.3650$, $P= 0.05$), place of residence($c^2= 2.38$ $P= 0.05$) type of family ($c^2= 0.396$, $P=0.05$), family monthly

income ($c^2= 1.33$, $P= 0.05$), educational status ($c^2= 0.3472$, $P= 0.05$), occupation ($c^2= 0.3968$, $P= 0.05$), diet pattern($c^2= 0.3676$, $P= 0.05$), number of pregnancy($c^2=0.089$, $P=0.05$),source of information($c^2= 0.240$, $P= 0.05$), in after test premeditated Fisher’s Exact Probability value is slighter than the table value for socio demographic characteristics therefore H_2 : is rejected for all socio demographic characteristics.

Table 4 Relationship among after-Test Awareness Scores and Selected their Socio-Demographic Characteristics N=50

SL	Socio Demographic Characteristics.	Df	Chi- square	Tablevalue	P value	Association
1.	Age	1	1.281	3.84	0.05	Insignificant
2.	Religion	1	0.3650	3.84	0.05	Insignificant
3.	Place of residence	1	2.38	3.84	0.05	Insignificant
4.	Type of family	1	0.396	3.84	0.05	Insignificant
5.	Family monthly income	1	1.33	3.84	0.05	Insignificant
6.	Educational status	1	0.3472	3.84	0.05	Insignificant
7	Occupation	1	0.3968	3.84	0.05	Insignificant
8	Diet pattern	1	0.3676	3.84	0.05	Insignificant
9	Number of pregnancy	1	0.089	3.84	0.05	Insignificant
10	Source of information	1	0.240	3.84	0.05	Insignificant

Df= degree of freedom

NS= Not Significant

IV. DISCUSSION

The present study was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of Planned Teaching Programmer on knowledge regarding extraction and preservation of breast milk among antenatal mothers. In order to achieve the objectives of the present study, pre experimental one group pre-test post-test without control group design with an evaluative approach was adopted. The sample was selected by purposive sampling technique. The sample comprised of 50 antenatal mothers and the data were collected from them before and after the administration of PTP. The overall findings reveal that the post- test knowledge score was more when compared to the pre-test knowledge score, the considered t value (19.97) is greatly elevated than table ‘t’ value (1.96) therefore the Hypothesis: H_1 : There is a considerable dissimilarity among before-test and after-test awareness marks of antenatal women about extraction and preservation of breast milk. The considered Chi-square value is smaller than table value for all socio demographic characteristics. This subject was encouraged by A quasi-experimental study which carried on postnatal mothers in Melmaruvathur, Tamilnadu by Ms. G. ELAIYAMUDHA, in April - 2012. With the objectives to know the impact of STP on extraction and preservation of breast milk among 60 employed postnatal women. Pre investigational one group pre test post test research design had been used for this study. PTP was given about extraction and preservation of breast milk via charts, posters and handouts. The information collected and its analysis reflect that, on the pre test (8.3%) women had moderate awareness, (91.7%)

women had insufficient awareness, in the before test (13.3%) had fair attitude, (86.07%) women had poor attitude. After test (60%) women had good attitude (40%) had fair attitude. After evaluation 40 (66.7%) women had adequate awareness, (33.33%) women had moderate information and. Paired‘t’ test score of knowledge was 51.69. Paired‘t’ test score of attitude was 34.75. There was a considerable co- relation among post test knowledge and attitude. The study concludes that planned teaching program has effect on extraction and preservation of breast milk.

V. LIMITATIONS

The study was confined to antenatal mothers in specific selected healthcare centres, which imposes limits on generalization. The sample for the study was limited to 50 antenatal mothers, thus restricting the statistical inferences of results. The structured feedback form was used to gather the information, restricting the respondents from providing adequate information about extraction and preservation of breast milk.

VI. CONCLUSION

The attempt was helpful in assessing understanding about extraction and preservation of breast milk among antenatal women presence in department of OBG at Hanagal Shree Kumareshwar Hospital and research centre, Bagalkote, Karnataka. On the whole study results discovered that the after test mean percentage scores of antenatal women (82.80%) was comparatively higher than the pretest mean

percentage scores of antenatal women (43`26%). Hence it was concluded that planned education programme has result on extraction and preservation of breast milk.

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➤ *Contribution of Authors:*

- **Research concept-** Jayashree Awarsang
- **Research design-** Netravathi, Dr. Kamala K.N
- **Supervision-** Jayashree Awarsang, Dr. Kamala K.N, Dr. Deelip Somaninga Natekar.
- **Materials-** Netravathi.
- **Data Collection:** Netravathi.
- **Data analysis and Interpretation-** Netravathi.
- **Literature search-** Netravathi.
- **Writing article-** Netravathi
- **Critical review-** - Jayashree Awarsang, Dr. Kamala K.N, Dr. Deelip Somaninga Natekar
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- **Final approval-** Netravathi, Jayashree Awarsang, Dr. Kamala K.N, Dr. Deelip Somaninga Natekar.

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